

1 **PPARG expression change is associated with trophectoderm specification in embryonic stem**
2 **cells.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 PPARG as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Majithia, A.R., Tsuda, B., Agostini, M., Gnanapradeepan, K., Rice, R., Peloso, G., Patel, K.A.,
12 Zhang, X., Broekema, M.F., Patterson, N. and Duby, M., 2016. Prospective functional classification of all
13 possible missense variants in PPARG. Nature genetics, 48(12), pp.1570-1575.
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28